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Abstract

When you hear the words “psychological testing,” all kinds of questions and thoughts may run through your mind. What will they ask? Will my answers be considered right or wrong? If my answers are wrong, what will that say about me? Psychologists use psychological testing in the same way medical doctors use lab work, X-rays, and physical exams: to determine the cause of your symptoms and recommend treatment, when necessary.

Key words: test, aspects, testology

Introduction

Psychological testing is the basis for mental health treatment. These tools are often used to measure and observe a person's behaviors, emotions, and thoughts. Tests are performed by a psychologist who will evaluate the results to determine the cause, severity, and duration of your symptoms. This will guide them in creating a treatment plan that meets your needs. Tests can either be objective or projective:

- Objective testing involves answering questions with set responses like yes/no or true/false.
- Projective testing evaluates responses to ambiguous stimuli in the hopes of uncovering hidden emotions and internal conflicts.

Both provide valuable insight into your symptoms and help psychologists see your overall level of functioning and distress. Psychological tests can include formal, or “norm-referenced,” tests to measure your ability to comprehend different concepts. They can come in the form of checklists and questionnaires. Each test measure ensures the reliability, validity, and objectivity necessary to avoid bias in scoring or interpreting your results. During a **psychological evaluation**, assessments may also be used to help diagnose and treat mental health conditions. Assessments include standardized tests as well as informal tests, such as:

- surveys
- clinical interviews
- observational data
- medical exams
- previous educational and medical history

Psychological testing can be recommended for a number of reasons including diagnosing mental health conditions and identifying troubling behavior. According to the **American Psychiatric Association**, the following symptoms may indicate that a psychological test may be needed:

- increased social withdrawal
- nervousness

- changes in mood
- difficulty completing normal tasks
- a dramatic change in sleep and eating habits
- problems with concentration

Other uses for psychological testing include:

- screening job applicants
- organizational development
- academic placement

Psychologists use testing to examine a variety of factors, including emotional intelligence, personality, mental aptitude, and neurological functioning. Here's a more in-depth look at the types of testing available and the most commonly used tests for each category.

Conclusion

Psychological assessment — also known as psychological testing — is done to help a psychologist better understand an individual and provide valuable insights into the individual's behavior, skills, thoughts and personality. Psychological testing commonly includes intelligence testing, personality testing, and skills testing, among other areas. Psychological assessment is never focused on a single test score or number. Every person has a range of competencies that can be evaluated through a number of methods. A psychologist is there to evaluate the competencies as well as the limitations of the person, and report on them in an objective but helpful manner. A psychological assessment report will not only note weaknesses found in testing, but also the individual's strengths.

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